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Left running head: Metformin Therapy in Type 2 Diabetes and Heart Failure

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Metformin Improves Glycemic Control and Postprandial Metabolism and Enhances Postprandial Glucagon-like peptide 1 Secretion in Patients With Type 2 Diabetes and Heart Failure: A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial

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This randomized trial tested the effect of metformin on glycemic control and cardiac function in patients with heart failure (HF) and type 2 diabetes while evaluating intestinal effects on selected gut microbiome products reflected by trimethylamine-N-oxide (TMAO) and gut-derived incretins. Metformin treatment improved glycemic control and postprandial metabolism and enhanced postprandial glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1) secretion but did not influence cardiac function or the TMAO levels. Metabolic effects of metformin in HF may be mediated by an

improvement in intestinal endocrine function and enhanced secretion of the gut-derived incretin GLP-1.

[main text]

Chronic heart failure (HF) is a growing health problem, and type 2 diabetes is one of the strongest risk factors for its development (1). Regardless of recent improvements in care, the prognosis of HF is ominous, and 50% of people diagnosed with HF die within 5 years. The prognosis of HF in individuals with type 2 diabetes is even worse (1,2). Along with sodium–glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors, metformin is the first line treatment for type 2 diabetes in patients with HF (1), based on multiple observational studies demonstrating improved survival and lower all-cause mortality in patients with type 2 diabetes and HF treated by metformin when compared to other type 2 diabetes treatments (3,4).

Although metformin is often used for HF with type 2 diabetes, its cardiovascular effects remain only partially understood (5). Similarly, the detailed mechanisms of action of metformin are unclear. The majority of ingested metformin (>80%) is not absorbed and remains in the gut, which may be relevant or even necessary for many of its effects (6). Based on previous studies in humans (7), it has been suggested that the benefits of metformin may be mediated by direct effects in the gut. These direct intestinal effects may be related to changes in the gut microbiome (8) or to modulation of secretion of intestinal incretin hormones such as glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1) and peptide YY (PYY) (9).

Trimethylamine-N-oxide (TMAO) is an organic compound formed in the liver from trimethylamine, a product exclusively generated by the intestinal microbiota (1). Increased plasma TMAO is linked to greater risk of death, myocardial infarction, or stroke (10). In patients with HF, plasma TMAO levels are increased compared to control subjects and are predictive of increased risk of mortality independent of cardiorenal indexes (11).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of metformin on metabolic control and cardiovascular and intestinal functions, as reflected by TMAO and incretins, in patients with HF and type 2 diabetes using the rigor of a randomized, placebo-controlled crossover trial.

Research Design and Methods

This was a single-center trial consisting of two treatment periods. Participants were instructed to adhere to ordinary lifestyle habits and avoid changes in food intake, alcohol consumption, and exercise during the study duration.

Study Oversight

The trial was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the International Conference on Harmonisation Good Clinical Practice guidelines and was approved by local authorities. An independent ethics committee approved the clinical protocol. The study was registered with ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT01690091), and all participants provided written informed consent before study entry.

Study Design

The study was a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, crossover trial of 7 months' duration testing the effects of 3 months of metformin therapy versus placebo. Patients were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive either metformin or placebo. After 3 months of treatment, there was a 1-month washout period, and participants were then switched to the other study arm for an additional 3 months.

Study Participants

Adults with HF and reduced left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) who were 40–70 years of age with a BMI of 20–35 kg/m², an A1C between 5.8 and 8.1% (40 and 54 mmol/mol), and a new diagnosis of type 2 diabetes (previously untreated) were enrolled. HF was defined as known diagnosis of HF of >6 months duration with a history of hospitalization for HF at any time in the past (including treatment with parenteral diuretics), stable pharmacotherapy for >30 days, chronic diuretic treatment (thiazides or furosemide) and LVEF <50%. Type 2 diabetes was defined as medical history and treatment of type 2 diabetes or A1C ≥5.7% (39 mmol/mol) plus fasting plasma glucose ≥100 mg/dL (5.6 mmol/L) in venous plasma or A1C 5.7% (39 mmol/mol) plus random plasma glucose ≥140 mg/dL (7.8 mmol/L) in venous plasma, or plasma glucose

measured at 120 minutes during an oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) ≥ 140 mg/dL (7.8 mmol/L). An OGTT was indicated if only one of the criteria was met. Adequate treatment was initiated in cases of impaired glycemic control (A1C ≥ 65 mmol/mol [6.5%] or hyperglycemia ≥ 270 mg/dL [15 mmol/L]).

Individuals with planned cardiac surgery during the study were excluded from the trial, as were those with uncontrolled thyroid disease, those treated with insulin or oral hypoglycemic agents 2 months before the enrollment, pregnant or breastfeeding women, women capable of conceiving without adequate contraception, individuals with anemia (hemoglobin < 100 g/L), as well as those with an estimated glomerular filtration rate < 42 mL/min/1.73 m², atrial fibrillation, drug or alcohol abuse, or the presence of any other health condition that could, in the investigators' opinion, distort the yield and consistency of the data.

Randomization and Interventions

Participants were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive either metformin or placebo for 3 months. Then, after a 1-month washout period (116 half-lives for metformin), the medication was changed to the other treatment for another 3 months. Randomization was based on a computer-generated randomization protocol.

During treatment, the initial dose of metformin (Siofor 1,000 mg [Berlin – Chemie AG Menarini Group, Berlin, Germany]) or placebo (1,000 mg [Favea, Koprivnice, Czech Republic]) was 500 mg/day. After 1 week, the dose was increased to 1,000 mg/day. After 14 days, the dose was increased to 2,000 mg/day administered in two doses in the morning and the evening. Placebo tablets were identical in appearance and could not be distinguished from the metformin tablets.

Primary and Secondary Outcomes

The primary outcome was insulin sensitivity (glucose metabolic clearance rate [MCR]), measured by a hyperinsulinemic isoglycemic clamp. The secondary outcomes included markers of cardiac function assessed by echocardiography and spiroergometry, postprandial secretion of intestinal peptides measured during a standard meal test, glycemic control assessed by A1C, and concentrations of TMAO.

Study Procedures

All participants underwent a standardized panel of metabolic and cardiovascular tests three times (at baseline and at the end of the intervention periods at 3 and 7 months) in a highly controlled inpatient setting, as well as an initial medical examination, blood sampling, meal test, echocardiography, spiroergometry, and hyperinsulinemic isoglycemic clamp. All participants fasted for a minimum of 8 hours before each study visit. Symptoms were scored using the standardized Minnesota Living with Heart Failure (MLHF) questionnaire (12).

Anthropometric Measures and Blood Pressure

Height and weight were measured using a stadiometer calibrated scale accurate to 0.1 kg. Blood pressure was measured in a seated position using a digital monitor (Omron HEM907XL, Omron, Kyoto, Japan) three times at 5-minute intervals. A mean value was calculated from the last two measurements.

3-Hour Hyperinsulinemic Isoglycemic Clamp

A teflon cannula (Venflon; Viggo, Helsingborg, Sweden) was inserted into an antecubital vein for the infusion of all test substances. A second cannula was inserted into a wrist vein for blood sampling. A stepwise primed-continuous insulin infusion (1 mU/kg body weight/min of Actrapid HM [Novo Nordisk, Copenhagen, Denmark]) was administered to acutely raise and maintain the plasma concentration of insulin at ~ 75 $\mu\text{U}/\text{mL}$. Blood glucose levels during the clamps was maintained at 5.5–8 mmol/L (99–144 mg/dL) by continuous infusion of 15% glucose. Arterialized blood glucose levels were determined every 5 minutes, and the infusion rate was adjusted accordingly. Insulin sensitivity was estimated as MCR (i.e., the amount of glucose (mg/kg body weight/minute) needed to maintain a stable blood glucose level during the last 20 minutes of the clamp.

Standard Meal Test

Blood samples were drawn in the fasting state and then at 30, 60, 120, and 180 minutes after a standard breakfast (cheese gourmet sandwich, 180 g, containing 452.8 kcal, including 49.2 g

carbohydrate, 18.5 g protein, and 18.8 lipids, including 6.8 g saturated fatty acids, 6.0 g monounsaturated fatty acids, and 5.0 g polyunsaturated fatty acids.

Echocardiography and Ventriculo-Vascular Coupling

A detailed quantification of the systolic and diastolic function of the ventricles, analysis of myocardial deformation (speckle-tracking), and quantification of left atrial volume were performed (System Vivid 7, GE, SW Echopac). Left ventricular end-systolic elastance (Ees) was determined by the single-beat technique of Chen based on measured stroke volume, ejection fraction, blood pressure, and systolic time intervals (13). Effective arterial elastance (Ea) was estimated from end-systolic pressure/stroke volume. End-systolic pressure was estimated as 0.9 times the systolic blood pressure; ventriculo-vascular coupling was estimated by Ees/Ea ratio as previously reported (14).

Symptom-Limited Bicycle Spiroergometry

This procedure was performed twice on two consecutive days during each hospitalization. Quantification of cardiovascular reserve using peak oxygen consumption (V_{\max} Encore 29S, load 25W/25W for 3 minutes).

Analytical Methods

Plasma glucose was analyzed using the Beckman Analyzer glucose-oxidase method (Beckman Instruments, Inc., Fullerton, CA), and A1C was assessed by a Bio-Rad Haemoglobin A1c Column Test (Bio-Rad Laboratories GmbH, Munich, Germany). Plasma immunoreactive insulin and C-peptide concentrations were determined using insulin and C-peptide immunoradiometric assay kits (Immunotech, Prague, Czech Republic). Plasma lipid levels were measured using enzymatic methods (Roche, Basel, Switzerland). HDL cholesterol was measured after double precipitation with dextran and magnesium chloride. LDL cholesterol was estimated using the Friedewald equation if triglycerides were within normal limits. Inflammatory markers and gastrointestinal hormones were determined by multiplex immunoanalyses based on the xMAP technology using Milliplex Map Human Metabolic Hormone Magnetic Bead Panel (HMHEMAG-34K; Millipore, Billerica, MA) and Luminex 100 IS instrument (Luminex Corp., Austin, TX). The concentration of

methylglyoxal was determined after derivatization with 1,2-diaminobenzene using a high-performance liquid chromatography method with fluorescence detection. TMAO was quantified with the use of an ultraperformance liquid chromatography coupled to electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry.

Statistical Analysis

Sample size was calculated with a power analysis for the primary outcome based on previous clamp studies in similar populations (15,16). Assuming a 25% improvement in baseline glucose MCR (estimate 4.0 ± 1.5 mg/kg/min) with $\alpha = 0.05$ and $\beta = 0.80$, the estimated sample size was $n = 37$.

Data reported here are expressed as mean \pm SD unless otherwise indicated. The effects of metformin versus placebo on measured variables were tested by Friedman ANOVA. Changes were calculated for placebo and metformin treatment compared with pre-treatment levels, as well as the difference between metformin and placebo. Spearman correlation coefficients were used to express the relationship between variables. All tests were two-sided, and $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Of 539 patients screened, 45 qualified and were randomized, with 39 completing the study (Supplementary Figure S1). The baseline values of all tracked outcomes and their changes in response to metformin and placebo in all study completers are shown in Table 1. The mean age of the study participants was 58 ± 8.4 years, 11% (5 of 45) were women, the mean BMI was 32.3 ± 5.1 kg/m², and the mean LVEF was $33.6 \pm 12.0\%$.

Primary Outcome

Insulin sensitivity, measured as glucose MCR during hyperinsulinemic isoglycemic clamp, tended to increase on metformin by 0.73 ± 0.97 mg/kg/min, but this increase was not significantly different from placebo ($P = 0.074$).

Secondary Outcomes

Cardiovascular Effects

Compared with placebo, metformin did not affect clinical symptoms quantified by the MLHF questionnaire (Table 1). No change was observed in left ventricular end-diastolic dimensions, indicating a neutral effect of metformin on the eccentric remodeling of the left ventricle (LV). LVEF did not change, but Ees, which reflects contractility, slightly decreased after metformin compared to placebo ($P = 0.026$). There were no differences in systemic arterial load, measured by Ea, or ventricular-vascular coupling between metformin and placebo. The ratio E/e' (the ratio between early mitral inflow velocity and mitral annular early diastolic velocity), which reflects the left ventricular filling pressure, also remained unchanged after both treatments, and there was no effect of metformin on brain natriuretic peptide (BNP) or left atrial volume (Table 1).

Effects on Aerobic Capacity

Exercise tolerance, as assessed by peak oxygen consumption (VO_2), slightly decreased during both interventions, with no difference between the treatments ($P = 0.118$; Table 1). Peak diastolic blood pressure decreased during both interventions compared with baseline, with no difference between the treatments ($P = 0.88$).

Effects on Glycemic Control

Fasting plasma glucose and A1C decreased on metformin, and these changes were significant compared with placebo, with effect sizes -7 ± 20 mg/dL (-0.38 ± 1.1 mmol/L, $P = 0.001$) and $-0.30 \pm 0.49\%$ (-3.39 ± 5.33 mmol/mol, $P < 0.001$), respectively (Figure 1A).

Effects on TMAO and Postprandial Incretin Response

No significant change in TMAO levels was observed during either treatment, and no association was detected between changes in TMAO and changes in metabolic or cardiac functions.

Postprandial metabolic control was evaluated using a standard meal test, and data were expressed as total area under curve (AUC). Metformin significantly decreased the plasma glucose AUC compared with placebo (effect size -2.7 ± 4.2 mmol/L/h, $P < 0.001$) (Figure 1B), as well as insulin AUC (effect size -47 ± 95.8 mIU/L/h, $P < 0.001$). Postprandial C-peptide did not

change during metformin therapy compared to placebo. Postprandial glucagon levels increased during metformin therapy, but the change was not significantly different from placebo ($P = 0.062$). Postprandial GLP-1 and PYY concentrations significantly increased during metformin therapy compared with placebo (effect sizes for AUC 53 ± 62.5 , $P < 0.001$ [Figures 1C and 2A] and 107.5 ± 164 , $P < 0.001$ [Figures 1D and 2B], respectively).

Safety

In general, the patients were clinically stable and were not developing cardiac decompensation during metformin therapy or placebo. Five of the six patients that discontinued treatment did so during the placebo phase, and one discontinued treatment during the metformin phase.

Discussion

This single center, randomized, placebo-controlled crossover study examined the effect of 3-month treatment with metformin on glycemic control, insulin resistance, and cardiac function in patients with type 2 diabetes and chronic HF. Compared with placebo, metformin treatment improved glycemic control, reduced postprandial glycemic and insulin response to a standard test meal, and increased postprandial secretion of the incretins GLP-1 and PYY. No significant changes in cardiac function or TMAO were observed, and there was no significant association between serum TMAO concentration and any of the measured metabolic or cardiorespiratory outcomes.

Effect of Metformin on Insulin Sensitivity and Glycemic Control

Insulin sensitivity tended to increase on metformin, but this increase was not significantly different from placebo. This study confirmed the efficacy of metformin in improving glycemic control and glucose metabolism, as well as its safety in patients with HF. Administration of metformin was accompanied by a decrease in A1C, a reduction in the postprandial glucose load measured as glucose AUC during a standard meal test, an increase in postprandial GLP-1 and PYY secretion, and a trend toward higher insulin sensitivity, measured by a hyperinsulinemic clamp.

Metformin has been shown to exert its major effects through inhibition of liver glucose production. Enhanced glucose disposal, reflecting the whole body sensitivity, has also been noted in some studies (17). Decreased postprandial insulin levels with preserved C-peptide concentrations during metformin therapy suggest changes in insulin clearance (18).

Although the mechanism of action of metformin is not completely understood, it improves glycemic control, reduces weight, and tends to reduce insulin resistance. Metformin has been previously shown to increase insulin sensitivity in people with HF who do not have diabetes (19), although its insulin-sensitizing effects were not confirmed in another trial (20). Even in patients with HF without diabetes, insulin resistance represents a strong independent predictor of mortality and is associated with worse symptoms and more impaired exercise capacity (21).

Effect of Metformin on Cardiac Function

Short-term 3-month therapy with metformin was safe and did not result in detectable changes in cardiovascular structure and exercise capacity, with the exception of a small reduction of LV contractility quantified by Ees. This change may reflect reduced myocardial oxygen consumption after metformin, recently documented by a positron emission tomography study in patients with HF (22). It is likely that cardioprotective effects of metformin (3,4) result from multiple small pleiotropic targets, rather than from a single detectable modification of cardiac structure and function. Favorable changes in cardiovascular structure or function could be observed only after a longer duration of metformin therapy. The lack of the effects of metformin on cardiac structure and exercise tolerance does not rule out the possibility of beneficial effects on clinical events in the long term. Similarly, therapy with β -blockers in patients with HF also may not improve peak VO_2 or BNP, but still leads to robust reduction in mortality over time. In a previous randomized study in people with HF without diabetes, metformin improved myocardial efficiency by reducing myocardial oxygen consumption (22), but there was no effect of metformin on VO_{2max} and cardiac structure and function in another study in people with HF without diabetes (19). Similarly, metformin had no effect on LV size and function in people with type 2 diabetes with a history of hypertension (23).

Effect of Metformin on TMAO

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study testing the effect of metformin on the gut microbiome–related metabolite TMAO and evaluating its relationship with glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity measured by the clamp technique in humans. We found no effect of metformin on TMAO levels. Previously, increased TMAO levels in individuals with HF have been associated with a 3.4-fold increase in mortality risk independent of cardiorenal function (11). However, large intra- and inter-individual variations in TMAO levels have been documented (24). Furthermore, elevated TMAO levels are more likely to be observed in HF with preserved ejection fraction than in HF with reduced ejection fraction (24) and seem to be increased in decompensated HF and congestion (25). Our results indicate that beneficial effects of metformin in HF are unlikely to be mediated by changes in intestinal microbiome–related production of TMAO.

Effect of Metformin on Incretin Secretion

This study demonstrated that metformin acts at least in part as a GLP-1 mimetic, increasing postprandial GLP-1 concentrations. Metformin's glucose-lowering effects may be partly explained by increased GLP-1 secretion (9), mainly resulting from its direct and AMP-activated protein kinase–dependent effect on GLP-1–secreting L cells in the small intestine (26). Metformin has been previously shown to increase the secretion of the another anorectic gut hormone, PYY, which is also produced by intestinal L cells, and these effects are believed to promote the modest weight loss observed with metformin (27).

The present results suggest that the primary effect of metformin action resides in the gut rather than in the circulation (28). Metformin modulates multiple components of the incretin axis and enhances expression of the GLP-1 receptor and related insulinotropic islet receptors through a mechanism requiring peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- α (29). Moreover, metformin enhances the expression of the genes encoding the receptors for both GLP-1 and glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP) in experimental models and also increases the effects of GIP and GLP-1 on insulin secretion from pancreatic β -cells (30). Finally, metformin has been shown to improve glycemic control by increasing incretins independent of changes in gluconeogenesis in young people with type 2 diabetes, suggesting an enteroinsular

mechanistic pathway (31). Confirming the beneficial effects of increased GLP-1 levels in this population, GLP-1 analogs seem to be a promising therapy option for people with HF and type 2 diabetes (32,33).

Strengths and Limitations

The main strengths of this study include its randomized, placebo-controlled design and multifaceted, in-depth cardiometabolic testing, including the 3-hour standard meal test, which provided insights into the postprandial dynamics of GLP-1 after metformin use that were in line with previous research (26).

The study was from a single center, and the sample size is modest, which may have reduced its power, but there was little signal of direct cardiac effect other than the modest reduction in Ees. The duration of treatment was relatively short, so we cannot address the effects of longer-term treatment with metformin. Although a larger sample size may have increased statistical significance of some variables such as MCR, the clinical significance of such an effect likely would have been negligible.

Conclusion

Metformin was found to be safe and to improve glycemic control in patients with HF and type 2 diabetes, but there were few direct effects of metformin on cardiovascular structure and function. Metformin did not affect the intestinal microbiome-derived toxic metabolite TMAO, but enhanced secretion of gut-derived incretins such as GLP-1, which may explain favorable metabolic effects with this agent.

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Duality of Interest

No potential conflicts of interest relevant to this article were reported.

Author Contributions

V.M., T.P., and H.K. designed and conducted the study and wrote the manuscript. E.H., K.V., J.V., J.B., O.K., T.C., M.S., L.T., J.K. Jr., and J.K., Sr. administered the intervention, collected the data, and reviewed the manuscript. BAB helped with data interpretation and reviewed the manuscript. MHa provided supervision and funding and reviewed the manuscript. MHi performed the statistical analysis and reviewed the manuscript. H.K. is the guarantor of this work and, as such, had full access to all the data in the study and takes responsibility for the integrity of the data and the accuracy of the data analysis.

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Figure 1. Changes in response to metformin and placebo in A1C (A), plasma glucose AUC (B), GLP-1 AUC (C), and PYY AUC (D). Data are mean \pm SEM, $n = 39$. Listed P values are from Friedman ANOVA. MET, metformin; PL, placebo.

Figure 2. Changes in response to metformin and placebo in postprandial concentrations of GLP-1 (A) and PYY (B). Data are mean \pm SEM, $n = 39$. Listed P values are from Friedman ANOVA. $*P < 0.05$ for a difference from baseline. MET, metformin; PL, placebo.

A

B

* $P < 0.05$ vs baseline

□ baseline
■ after MET
■ after PL

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Table 1. Baseline Values and Response to Metformin and Placebo Treatment

	Baseline	Metformin	Placebo	Δ Metformin- Δ Placebo	P
<i>Anthropometric measurements and laboratory tests</i>					
Weight, kg	96.9 \pm 19.9	94.6 \pm 19.6	95.4 \pm 20.0	-1.2 \pm 3.3	0.053
BMI, kg/m ²	32.3 \pm 5.1	31.6 \pm 5.2	31.9 \pm 5.2	-0.4 \pm 1.1	0.055
Waist circumference, cm	110 \pm 12.6	109 \pm 12.4	110 \pm 13.1	-0.7 \pm 4.7	0.243
Fasting plasma glucose, mg/dL	119 \pm 24	109 \pm 23	116 \pm 27	-7 \pm 20	0.001
Fasting plasma glucose, mmol/L	6.63 \pm 1.33	6.07 \pm 1.27	6.44 \pm 1.52	-0.38 \pm 1.1	0.001
A1C, %	6.4 \pm 0.71	6.2 \pm 0.50	6.5 \pm 0.82	-0.30 \pm 0.49	<0.001
A1C, mmol/mol	46.5 \pm 7.9	43.9 \pm 5.5	47.3 \pm 9.1	-3.39 \pm 5.33	<0.001
Triglycerides, mmol/L	2.04 \pm 1.03	2.15 \pm 0.97	2.22 \pm 0.96	-0.04 \pm 0.74	0.751
Total cholesterol, mmol/L	4.26 \pm 1.01	3.95 \pm 1.03	4.16 \pm 0.94	-0.2 \pm 0.82	0.177
LDL cholesterol, mmol/L	2.65 \pm 0.88	2.36 \pm 0.86	2.54 \pm 0.85	-0.18 \pm 0.73	0.099
HDL cholesterol, mmol/L	0.9 \pm 0.25	0.92 \pm 0.25	0.89 \pm 0.24	0.01 \pm 0.27	0.970
BNP, pg/mL	171 \pm 191	182 \pm 222	177 \pm 188	10.8 \pm 122	0.819
TMAO, μ M	2.78 \pm 1.42	3.45 \pm 1.61	3.00 \pm 1.52	0.45 \pm 2.17	0.246
Methylglyoxal, nmol/mL	0.37 \pm 0.11	0.30 \pm 0.12	0.32 \pm 0.12	-0.07 \pm 0.12	0.191
Euglycemic clamp MCR glucose, mg/kg/min	3.59 \pm 1.57	4.28 \pm 1.63	3.91 \pm 1.84	0.27 \pm 1.18	0.074
<i>Standard meal test</i>					
Plasma glucose AUC, mmol/L/h	23.7 \pm 5.65	20.5 \pm 3.7	23 \pm 6.62	-2.7 \pm 4.2	<0.001
Insulin AUC, mIU/L/h	172 \pm 117	128 \pm 68.8	173 \pm 11	-47 \pm 95.8	<0.001
C-peptide AUC, ng/mL/h	9.4 \pm 3.0	8.50 \pm 3.35	9.1 \pm 2.72	-0.63 \pm 2.40	0.101
Free fatty acid AUC, mmol/L/h	1.2 \pm 0.55	1.0 \pm 0.33	1.06 \pm 24.4	-0.05 \pm 0.4	0.608
Triglycerides AUC, mmol/L/h	7.27 \pm 3.27	7.12 \pm 2.9	7.42 \pm 3.15	-0.245 \pm 2.52	0.958
Glucagon AUC, pg/mL/h	192 \pm 152	207 \pm 142	198 \pm 153	11.8 \pm 48.8	0.062
Ghrelin AUC, pg/mL/h	154 \pm 248	127 \pm 85.7	144 \pm 154	-3.7 \pm 58	0.844
Leptin AUC, pg/mL/h	47,333 \pm 34,667	48,000 \pm 52,500	51,667 \pm 43,500	-4,400 \pm 26,167	0.035
GIP AUC, pg/mL/h	738 \pm 310	745 \pm 392	822 \pm 368	-47.2 \pm 353	0.402
GLP-1 AUC, pg/mL/h	89 \pm 105	146 \pm 116	92 \pm 73.5	53 \pm 62.5	<0.001
Pancreatic polypeptide AUC, pg/mL/h	1,392 \pm 673	1,463.3 \pm 703	1,433 \pm 673	31.2 \pm 310	0.465
PYY AUC, pg/mL/h	378 \pm 177	502 \pm 223	388 \pm 136	107.5 \pm 164	<0.001
<i>Cardiopulmonary exercise study</i>					
Resting heart rate/min	74.6 \pm 11.4	74.9 \pm 10.6	75.6 \pm 11	-0.23 \pm 11.5	0.444
Resting systolic blood pressure, mmHg	113 \pm 17.6	110 \pm 13.2	111 \pm 13.8	-3 \pm 17	0.411
Resting diastolic blood pressure, mmHg	72.6 \pm 12.1	73.1 \pm 10.3	73.4 \pm 11.5	-0.97 \pm 13.1	0.82

VO ₂ max, mL/kg/min	16 ± 3.95	15.4 ± 3.94	15.8 ± 3.76	-0.34 ± 1.44	0.118
Peak heart rate, min	109 ± 20.3	106 ± 22.1	108 ± 21.9	-2.11 ± 14.9	0.272
Peak systolic blood pressure, mmHg	143 ± 29.1	139 ± 24.9	141 ± 22.9	-0.97 ± 23	0.718
Peak diastolic blood pressure, mmHg	80 ± 15.7	73.3 ± 10.7	74.5 ± 11.5	-0.86 ± 11.9	0.883
Respiratory quotient	1.02 ± 0.12	0.97 ± 0.067	1.00 ± 0.07	-0.01 ± 0.069	0.268
VE/VCO ₂ slope	31.7 ± 10.1	31.1 ± 5.97	31.4 ± 5.74	0.06 ± 4.15	0.596
<i>Cardiac structure and function</i>					
LV end-diastolic diameter, mm	65.3 ± 8.7	63.6 ± 9.3	64.3 ± 8.0	-0.97 ± 4.3	0.201
LVEF, %	33.6 ± 12.0	35.2 ± 12.1	35.6 ± 10.2	-0.4 ± 7.75	0.601
Maximal left atrial volume, mL	92.1 ± 39.8	88.8 ± 42.7	88.8 ± 42.9	0.06 ± 28.2	0.950
Transmitral E wave, cm/s	62.3 ± 26.9	61.9 ± 22.9	61.7 ± 26.9	3.0 ± 16.6	0.451
E/e' ratio	11.6 ± 6.4	10.6 ± 4.98	10.7 ± 6.6	0.94 ± 3.3	0.088
MLHF questionnaire total score	26.3 ± 17.6	24.9 ± 17.7	25.8 ± 20.2	0.63 ± 14.8	0.278
<i>Ventricular-vascular coupling</i>					
LV Ees, mmHg/mL	1.01 ± 0.50	0.91 ± 0.32	1.04 ± 0.44	-0.12 ± 0.38	0.044
Effective Ea, mmHg/mL	1.65 ± 0.78	1.51 ± 0.52	1.61 ± 0.64	-0.10 ± 0.43	0.127
Ventricular-vascular coupling, Ees/Ea	0.63 ± 0.24	0.63 ± 0.20	0.66 ± 0.23	-0.03 ± 0.20	0.276
Unstressed LV volume, V ₀ , mL	27.1 ± 86	24.6 ± 85	24.5 ± 76	0.22 ± 34	0.967

Data are mean ± SD, $n = 39$. P values are from Friedman ANOVA.

Supplemental Figure S1. Flow-chart of study enrollment and participation during the study.

